

The Standard Electrode Potentials of the Gold Aqua Ions and the Stabilities of Gold(I) and Gold(III) Complexes in Aqueous Solution.

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The standard electrode potentials of the hypothetical diaqua gold(I) and tetraqua-gold(III) ions are approximated by means of Edwards' equation redefined using stability data for the chlorido and bromido complexes as basis. The following values are recommended: $E^\circ(\text{Au}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+, \text{Au}) = 1.83 \text{ V}$ and $E^\circ(\text{Au}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{3+}, \text{Au}) = 1.52 \text{ V}$. The use of the coefficient α in Edwards' equation as a softness parameter is discussed, and it is shown that it correlates well with Klopman's theoretical softness parameter. The softness or class (b) character increases in the order: $\text{Au(I)} < \text{Hg(II)} < \text{Au(III)}$.

THE standard potentials of several gold complexes are known from measurements with gold metal electrodes. Equilibrium between metallic gold, gold(I), and gold(III) must, however, be established before reliable results can be obtained. Gold(I) is stabilized so much in aqueous solution by soft ligands such as iodide and thiosulphate that the equilibrium concentration of gold(III) is negligible. In such complex systems the electrode potential of a gold metal electrode therefore refers to the standard potential of the gold(I) complex. In the case of harder ligands such as chloride, potential measurements with gold metal electrodes are hindered by the often slow attainment of equilibrium, e.g.

The standard potentials of the aqua gold(I), gold and the aqua gold(III), gold couples are not directly accessible from experiments since the hypothetical diaquagold(I) ion disproportionates to gold(III) species and metallic gold, and the hypothetical tetraquagold(III) ion has such a high acidity that it cannot exist in aqueous solution. This implies that stability constants of gold complexes can only be measured relative to one another. In contrast to the situation with aqueous solutions solvated gold(I) ions exist as such in several aprotic solvents, so that the stability of other gold(I) complexes in these media can be determined relative to the solvated gold(I) ions.

1. *Electrode potentials and stability data for gold(I) complexes.* The first quantitative studies of gold(I) complexes were Bodländer's determination of the standard potential of the dicyanidoaurate(I) ion¹ and N. Bjerrum and Kirschner's determination of that of the dithiocyanatoaurate(I) ion². Table 1 collects the known, directly determined standard potentials for complex of gold(I) in aqueous solution. The stability

constants β_2' calculated relative to the dichloridoaurate (I) ion are also given. The data show that gold(I) behaves as a typical soft acceptor.

TABLE 1—STANDARD POTENTIALS FOR COMPLEX GOLD (I) IONS: $\text{AuL}_2^- + e^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Au} + 2\text{L}^-$ GIVEN RELATIVE TO THE STANDARD HYDROGEN ELECTRODE, AND THE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE GOLD (I) COMPLEXES RELATIVE TO THE DICHLORIDOAUROATE(I) ION.

Ligand	t/°C	I	$E_{1,0}^\circ/\text{V}^a$	Ref.	$\log \beta_2'$
Cl ⁻	40	var.	+1.13	3	0
	20	var.	+1.119	4	
	25	var.	+1.113	5	
	25	0	+1.154	6	
	25	0	+1.148	7	
Br ⁻	60	var.	+0.964	8	3.29
	25	0	+0.963	9	
	25	0	+0.959	10	
	25	0	+0.960	11	
SCN ⁻	20	1.0	+0.689	2	8.31
	25	3.0	+0.670	12	
	25	0	+0.662	13	
I ⁻	25	var.	+0.578	14	9.73
NH ₃	25	10	+0.563	15	10.0
(NH ₂) ₂ CS	25	var.	+0.380	16	13.1
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	25	0	+0.153	17	16.9
Dpm ^b	25	1.0	+0.053	18	18.6
CN ⁻			-0.611	1	
	25		-0.600	19	
	25	var.	-0.48	30	27.6

^a Values for standard potentials assumed to be representative are italicized.

^b Diphenylphosphinobenzene-*m*-sulphonate.

a. *Comparison of stabilities of gold(I) complexes in aprotic and aqueous solutions.* The stability of the complexes of d^{10} metal ions other than gold(I) is known relative to the corresponding aqua ions. It is characteristic for these metal ions that their mean affinity for the halide and pseudohalide ions increases on going from subgroup II B to subgroup I B, *i.e.* from zinc(II) to copper(I) and from cadmium(II) to silver(I). One might therefore expect that gold(I) also has a higher affinity than mercury(II) for these ligands.

The stabilities of gold(I) complexes has been determined by potentiometric methods in acetonitrile²⁰ and in dimethylsulphoxide²¹. Gold(I) and copper (I) are the stable oxidation states in both of these media, in contrast to the situation in aqueous solution. Stability constants for these metal ions as well as for silver(I) and mercury(II) in water and dimethylsulphoxide are given in Table 2. It can be seen from the table that mercury(II) forms more stable complexes than gold(I) in dimethylsulphoxide, a trend which is also observed with acetonitrile as solvent²⁰. The gold(I) electrode potentials estimated in the present work show that this tendency is also followed for the halide complexes in water. However, the thiocyanate, cyanide and ammonia complexes of gold(I) are found to be more stable in water than those of mercury(II).

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR LINEAR COMPLEXES OF COPPER(I), SILVER(I), GOLD(I) AND MERCURY (II) IN WATER AND DIMETHYLSULPHOXIDE AT 25°C.

		Water			Dimethylsulphox.de			
		Cu(I)	Ag(I)	Hg(II)	Cu(I)	Ag(I)	Au(I)	Hg(II)
Cl ⁻	log β_2	6.0	5.4	13.2	12.0	11.7	18.0	21.2
	Ref.	22	23	24	32	33	21	34
Br ⁻	log β_2	6.2	7.2	17.3	9.6	12.0	16.6	22.2
	Ref.	25	23	24	32	33	21	34
I ⁻	log β_2	8.7	11	23.8	8.2	13.0		24.2
	Ref.	25	26	24	32	33		34
SCN ⁻	log β_2	11.0	8.3	16.9	9.3	8.4		16.1
	Ref.	27	28	29	32	33		34
CN ⁻	log β_2	21.7	20.9	32.5		23.4		
	Ref.	30	30	31		33		

In general, the magnitude of the stability constants increases on going from water to aprotic solvents. Table 2 shows that in some cases even the magnitude sequence for the stability constants of the halide complexes is altered. This is understandable, however, when one considers that the anionic ligands are solvated in water, the strength of hydrogen bonding for *e.g.* the halide ions decreasing in the order: chloride > bromide > iodide. In aprotic media there is no such possibility for hydrogen bonding and for this reason chloride has a relatively higher affinity for the metal ions than bromide, which again has a higher affinity than iodide. This explains the fact that the large differences in stability constants for the halide complexes of silver(I), gold(I), and mercury(II) which one observes for aqueous solution have almost vanished in these media.

Dimethylsulphoxide can coordinate through either the oxygen or the sulphur atom. However, structure determinations indicate that it coordinates to silver(I) and mercury(II) through oxygen²², whereas with the d^8 metal ions Pd(II)²³ and Pt(II)²⁴ it has been found to coordinate through the sulphur atom.

In order to use the data shown in Table 2 to estimate the stability constants of gold(I) complexes in aqueous solution plots were made of the known stability constants (log β_2) for the chlorido and bromido complexes in water *versus* the corresponding constants in dimethylsulphoxide. The resulting nearly linear correlations are shown in Fig. 1. Interpolation to the stability constants of gold(I) complexes in aqueous solution gave β_2 values of $10^{10.8} l^2/mol^2$ for the dichloridoaurate(I) ion and $10^{12.8} l^2/mol^2$ for the dibromidoaurate(I) ion, respectively. Combining these values of β_2 with the potentials for the halide complexes given in Table 1, the electrode potential for the $Au(H_2O)_2^+$, Au couple is calculated to be 1.77 and 1.67 V, respectively. This discrepancy shows, however, that the proposed linear relationship, like other linear relationships to be discussed in the following section, cannot bear closer examination.

Fig. 1. The stability constants of dichlorido and dibromido complexes of copper(I), silver(I) and mercury(II) in water *versus* their stabilities in dimethylsulphoxide.

b *Earlier attempts to estimate the standard potential of the aqua gold(I), gold couple.* Latimer²⁵ estimates the potential of the aqua gold(I), gold couple from a value for the solubility product of AuI obtained by extrapolation of the solubility products of CuI ($10^{-12} mol^2/l^2$) and of AgI ($10^{-16} mol^2/l^2$) to the solubility product of AuI. The value obtained in this way ($10^{-20} mol^2/l^2$), when combined with other data yields a value for the potential in question of 1.68 V. That Latimer's extrapolation is untenable has been pointed out by J. Bjerrum *et al.*¹⁸ and by Erenburg and Peshechevitskii²⁶.

J. Bjerrum *et al.*¹⁸ define the parameter

$$Q = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \log \beta_N(Cl^-) + \log 55}{\frac{1}{N} \log \beta_N(CN^-) - \frac{1}{N} \log \beta_N(Cl^-)}$$

where N is the characteristic coordination number of the metal ion. Q seems to vary regularly for the d^{10} metal ions and interpolation to Au(I) from Cu(I) via Ag(I) or from Tl(III) via Hg(II) gave in both cases a value for Q of ca. 0.7. Using this value for Au(I) the standard potential for the aqua gold(I), gold couple is calculated to be +2.12 V. However, Hancock *et al.*⁴⁰ have shown that Q does not vary regularly for other pairs of ligands such as I^-/CN^- and Cl^-/I^- .

Erenburg and Peshchevskii³⁹ find an approximately linear relationship between the standard potentials of the Au(I) complexes and those of Hg(II), Tl(III), Cu(I), Pt(II), and Au(III) with the ligands chloride, bromide, iodide, thiocyanate, and thiosulphate. On the basis of these 5 supposed relationships and the standard potentials for the 5 aqua systems (of which those for Pt(II) and Au(III) are not reliably known) they calculate an average value of 1.85 V for the electrode potentials of the aqua gold(I), gold couple.

Jorgensen and Pouradier⁴¹, and Hancock *et al.*^{40,42} assume that linear free relationships are valid only for the more closely related (group I B) metals Cu(I), Ag(I), and Au(I). An example of such a relationship is shown in Fig. 2, in which the potentials of the Au(I), Au couples for a series of ligands are plotted *versus* the potentials of the corresponding Ag(I), Ag couples. The dotted extrapolated line (drawn by Hancock *et al.*⁴⁰) indicates the aqua gold(I), gold couple to have a

Fig. 2. The potentials of Au(I), Au couples for a series of ligands as a function of the corresponding Ag(I), Ag couples.

standard potential of 1.67. The full line has the slope which according to Jorgensen and Pouradier⁴¹ reproduces the data. Extrapolation of this line indicates the potential for the aqua gold(I) system to be ca. 1.8 V. From a corresponding plot in which the standard potentials of the Au(I) complexes are plotted *versus* the Cu(I), Cu potentials, Hancock *et al.*⁴⁰ again find an extrapolated value for the standard potential of 1.67 V. However, the deviations of the points from a straight line are greater in this plot and a line could equally well be drawn to yield a value of ca. 1.8V.

c. *Estimation of the standard potential of the aqua gold(I), gold couple by use of Edwards' four parameter equation.* The use of linear free energy relationships such as those discussed in the foregoing sections for the subgroup I B metals and for two different solvents presupposes that the stability of the complexes in question can be expressed by equations of the form

$$\log \frac{K}{K_0} = S_A S_B \quad (1)$$

S_A is a parameter characteristic for each metal ion, S_B is a parameter characteristic for each ligand, K is the stability constant, and K_0 refers to the stability of the reference complex.

The fact that equations of this kind have been found to be approximately valid in many cases^{43,44}, is probably due to the fact that either the metal ions or the ligands were very similar in the majority of their properties and only exhibit minor differences in one property.

A more general equation with four parameters has been proposed by Pearson⁴⁵:

$$\log \frac{K}{K_0} = S_A S_B + \sigma_A \sigma_B \quad (2)$$

The product $S_A S_B$ is assumed to take account of the ionic contribution to the stability and $\sigma_A \sigma_B$ the covalent contribution. Thus σ_A and σ_B can be regarded as softness parameters for the cation and ligand, respectively. A similar four-parameter equation proposed by Edwards⁴⁶:

$$\log \frac{K}{K_0} = \alpha E_n + \beta H \quad (3)$$

is easy to use and contrary to equation (1) is applicable to stability constants of complexes in general.

The coefficients α and β in this equation are characteristic parameters for the metal ion whilst E_n and H are parameters for the ligands whose values are given relative to a chosen reference ligand. The stability constants are similarly defined relative to a corresponding complex of the chosen reference complex. Edwards⁴⁶ uses water as the reference ligand. However, when correlating the stabilities of complexes of metals

for which the aqua ions are unknown it is necessary to adopt a ligand other than water as reference. In the case of gold(I), the well-investigated dichloridoaurate(I) and dibromidoaurate(I) ions are convenient reference

complexes. Values of $\log \frac{K}{K_0}$ can then be replaced by

$\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'$, where β_2' are the cumulative stability constants relative to the dichloridoaurate(I) or dibromidoaurate(I) ions. The ligand parameters in the equation are defined by the expressions :

$$E_n = E^\circ(L^{v-}, \frac{1}{2}L_2^{(2v-2)}) - E^\circ(\text{ref.})$$

$$H = pK_a(\text{HL}) - pK_a(\text{ref.})$$

where $E^\circ(L^{v-}, \frac{1}{2}L_2^{(2v-2)})$ is the standard potential for the oxidative dimerisation of the ligand, $E^\circ(\text{ref.})$ refers, in the present example, to the values for chloride (1.36 V) or bromide (1.09 V) and $pK_a(\text{HL})$ corresponds to the acid dissociation constant of the protonated ligand. $pK_a(\text{ref.})$ has the value -6.1 for chloride⁴⁷ and a value of -7.2 was chosen for bromide^{43,48}. The parameter H can thus be regarded as a measure of the proton affinity of the ligand and E_n as a measure of its nucleophilic character. αE_n corresponds to the covalent affinity contribution $\sigma_A \sigma_B$ in equation (2) and βH to the ionic contribution $S_A S_B$. The quantity α can therefore be considered to provide a measure of the softness of the metal ion and β a measure of its hardness.

Introducing $\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'$ instead of $\log \frac{K}{K_0}$, equation (3) can be written as

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'}{H} = \alpha \frac{E_n}{H} + \beta \quad (4)$$

Those ligand standard potentials which cannot be measured directly, such as $E^\circ(\text{H}_2\text{O}, \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_4\text{O}_2^{2+})$ and $E^\circ(\text{NH}_3, \frac{1}{2} \text{N}_2\text{H}_6^{2+})$, have been estimated by Edwards⁴⁶ by various methods. In Tables 1 and 3 are given the

TABLE 3—LIGAND PARAMETERS TO EDWARDS' EQUATION DEFINED RELATIVE TO THE CHLORIDE AND TO THE BROMIDE IONS.

Ligand	$E^\circ(L^{v-}, \frac{1}{2}L_2^{(2v-2)})$	$pK_a(\text{HL})$	E_n/H^α	E_n/H^b
Cl ⁻	-1.36	-6.1		-0.25
Br ⁻	-1.09	-7.2	-0.25	
SCN ⁻	-0.77	-0.8	+0.11	+0.05
I ⁻	-0.54	-8.7	-0.27	-0.28
NH ₃	-0.76	+9.2	+0.04	+0.02
(NH ₂) ₂ CS	-0.42	-0.9	+0.18	+0.11
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	-0.08	+1.7	+0.16	+0.11
CN ⁻	+0.2	+9.4	+0.10	+0.08
OH ⁻	-1.0	+15.7	+0.02	+0.00
H ₂ O	-2.60	-1.7	-0.28	-0.27

^a E_n/H calculated with chloride as reference.

^b E_n/H calculated with bromide as reference.

data necessary to calculate the quantities $\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'/H$ and E_n/H for the various gold(I) complexes relative to the ligands chloride and bromide. Plots with $\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'/H$ as ordinate versus E_n/H as abscissa are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the points lie close to straight lines as predicted by equation (4), and values of $\alpha = 6.5$ and $\beta = 0.1$ valid for Au(I) can be read off from the figure. The stability constant for the dichloridoaurate(I) ion is obtained as follows: E_n/H has the value -0.28 for water (see Table 3). Reading from the line in the upper part of Fig. 3 this corresponds to $\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2'/H = -1.70$. In order to calculate

Fig. 3. Edwards' plot for Au(I). In the upper part the reference ligand is chloride, in the lower it is bromide.

$\beta_2 (= [\text{AuCl}_2^-]/[\text{Au}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+][\text{Cl}^-]^2)$ we use the relationship :

$$\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2' = -4 \times 1.70 = -\frac{1}{2} \log \beta_2 - \log 55$$

from which $\log \beta_2$ is found to be 11.5. A similar calculation gives $\log \beta_2 = 14.7$ for the dibromidoaurate(I) ion. Combination of these stability constants with the respective standard potentials for the complex ions gives a value of 1.83 V for the standard electrode potential of the diauagold(I) ions in both cases. We consider this value to be more reliable than the values ranging from 1.67 to 2.12 V which were discussed in the previous section.

In Table 4 are given the values for the cumulative stability constants of the various linear gold(I) complexes using the value of 1.83 V for the electrode potential of the diaquagold(I) ion. These values replace those given previously by J. Bjerrum *et al.*^{18,43,49}. The ratio between the values of $\frac{1}{N} \log \beta_N + \log 55$ for the ammine, cyanido and pyridine complexes of metal ions has been found⁴⁹ to be approximately 1 : 1.7 : 0.6 except in a few cases Ru(II)⁵⁰, Pd(II)⁵¹ where there is the possibility of strong π -back donation of cyanide and pyridine to the metal ion; using the present value of 1.83 V for the standard potential of the Au(H₂O)₂⁺, Au couple one calculates the above ratio to be 1.74 : 1 for the cyanido-relative to the ammine gold(I) complex.

TABLE 4—STABILITY OF THE LINEAR GOLD (I) COMPLEXES RELATIVE TO THE DIAQUAGOLD (I) ION CALCULATED WITH E°(Au(H₂O)₂⁺, Au)=1.83 V.

	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	SCN ⁻	I ⁻	NH ₃	(NH ₂) ₂ CS	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	Dpm	CN ⁻
$\log \beta_2$	11	15	20	21	21	24	28	30	39

TABLE 5—STANDARD POTENTIALS FOR COMPLEX GOLD(III) IONS: AuL₄⁻+3e⁻→Au+4L⁻ GIVEN RELATIVE TO THE STANDARD HYDROGEN ELECTRODE, AND THE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE GOLD(III) COMPLEXES RELATIVELY TO THE TETRACHLOROAUROATE(III) ION.

Ligand	t/°C	I	E _{3,0} ⁰ /V ^a	Ref.	log β ₄ '
Cl ⁻	40	var.	+1.01	3	
	20	var.	+0.994	4	
	25	var.	+0.994	5	
	25	0	+1.002	6	0
	25	0	+0.995	7	
Br ⁻	60	var.	+0.87	8	
	25	0	+0.856	9	
	25	0	+0.854	10	7.50
SCN ⁻	25	0	+0.852	11	
	20	1.0	+0.660	2	
	25	0	+0.636	13	18.55
I ⁻	25	var.	(+0.56)	54	22.4
OH ⁻	25		(+0.48)	55	26.4
NH ₃	25	10	+0.325	15	34.3
CN ⁻	25	var.	(-0.10)	56	56.0

^a Values for standard potentials assumed to be representative are italicized. Potentials given in brackets are calculated from indirect experiments.

2. Electrode potentials and stability data for gold(III) complexes.

Relatively little is known concerning the stability constants and standard potentials of gold(III) complexes. Jirsa and Jelinek^{52,53} measured the potentials of gold electrodes in solutions prepared by dissolving Au(OH)₃ in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 0.5 M HNO₃, and found the standard potential for "Au³⁺" in these two media to be 1.39 and 1.37 V, respectively. They determined also the solubility of Au(OH)₃ in 0.5 M HNO₃ and Latimer⁵⁰ made use of these data in estimating the standard potential of the aqua gold(III) system to be 1.50 V. As will be seen later, the latter estimate appears to be rather good.

c. Estimation of the standard potential of the aqua gold(III), gold couple by use of Edwards' equation. As mentioned in the introduction potential measurements in solutions of gold complexes require equilibrium adjustment between Au(III), Au(I), and metallic gold. Measurements of standard potentials of gold(III) complexes are further complicated by the fact that Au(III) oxidizes soft ligands. The known, directly measured potentials of gold(III) complexes are collected in Table 5 together with potentials calculated from hydrolysis data and other indirect experimental results. The data necessary to examine the validity of equation (4) are given in Tables 3 and 5, and a plot of $\frac{1}{4} \log \beta_4'/H$ versus E_N/H is shown in Fig. 4. The 6 points in the figure are seen to lie close to a straight line and values of α=7.4 and β=0.2 for Au(III) can be read from the figure. From a calculation analogous to that on the Au(I) case, log β₄' for the tetrachloroaurate(III) ion is found to be 26.5. Combination of this value with the standard potential of the tetrachloroaurate(III) ion gives the value 1.52 V for the standard electrode potential of the tetraquagold(III) ion, a value

Fig. 4. Edwards' plot for Au(III). Reference ligand is chloride.

which agrees well with Latimer's estimate of 1.50 V. Finkelstein and Hancock⁵⁶ assume that the standard potentials of Au(III) complexes vary linearly with those of the corresponding complexes of Pt(II) and Pd(II). However, this is a rather questionable assumption and their estimated value of 1.39 V is probably much too low. Using the value E°(Au(H₂O)₄³⁺, Au)=1.52 V the cumulative stability constants for various gold(III) complexes given in Table 6 are obtained. These values should replace estimates given in the literature, notably those of J. Bjerrum⁴⁹ for the cyanido- and ammine complexes (which are based on a wrong value for the

stability constant of the cyanido complex⁵⁷ and an average ratio 1.7 : 1 for $\frac{1}{N} \log \beta_N + \log 55$ for the

cyanido relative to that for the ammine complex). There is probably very little π -back bonding in the cyanido complex of Au(III) and it therefore seems reasonable that the ratio of $\frac{1}{4} \log \beta_4 + \log 55$ for the latter to that for the ammonia complex in the gold(III) system (*viz.* 1.33) is lower than that for the gold(I) system (*viz.* 1.74). However, it must be remembered that the value for β_4 in the cyanide system is only an uncertain estimate⁵⁸ and is probably too low.

TABLE 6—STABILITY OF THE SQUARE PLANAR GOLD (III) COMPLEXES RELATIVE TO THE TETRAQUAGOLD (III) ION CALCULATED WITH $E^0(\text{Au}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{3+}, \text{Au}) = 1.52$ V.

	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	SCN ⁻	I ⁻	OH ⁻	NH ₃	CN ⁻
$\log \beta_4$	26	34	45	49	53	60	82

3. The parameter α in Edwards' equation as a quantitative measure of metal ion softness.

Ahrlund, Chatt and Davies⁵⁸ distinguish between class (a) and class (b) character of cations and anions. It has more recently become popular, following Pearson⁵⁹, to speak about "hardness" and "softness" and various authors^{60,61,62} have tried to establish quantitative measures for softness. We propose here the use of α in Edwards' equation as a softness parameter for cations. In a recent paper⁶³ one of the present authors made a critical survey of α and β values for a series of softer metal ions. These values, together with those obtained for Au(I) and Au(III) in the present work, are given in Table 7 and are compared with values of Klopman's softness parameter derived from polyelectron perturbation theory. The values of α and β in parentheses have not been published previously. They are uncertain estimates based on a rather incomplete knowledge of the cumulative stability constants of the fluoride and hydroxide complexes. The fact that H⁺ has $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 1$ is a direct consequence of the way in which the parameters of Edwards' equation are defined.

From a closer examination of Table 7 it is evident that there is reasonably good correspondence between Klopman's parameter σ_K and Edwards' parameter α , and it is therefore reasonable to regard α as an experimental softness parameter. β on the other hand behaves qualitatively like a hardness parameter but is experimentally less well-defined. For this and other reasons we cannot agree with Yingst and McDaniel⁶⁴ who propose to use the ratio α/β as a softness parameter.

TABLE 7—COMPARISON OF KLOPMAN'S SOFTNESS PARAMETER WITH THE PARAMETERS FROM EDWARDS' EQUATION.

	σ_K	α	β
AJ ³⁺	-6.0	(-2.8)	(0.9)
Fe ²⁺	-2.2	(-0.7)	(0.8)
Ga ³⁺	-1.5	(-0.5)	(0.8)
H ⁺	-0.4	0	1
In ³⁺	-	(0.4)	(0.6)
Zn ²⁺	-	1.2	0.2
Cu ²⁺	0.5	1.6	0.3
Cd ²⁺	2.0	2.2	0
Cu ⁺	2.3	3.4	0.1
Ag ⁺	2.8	3.5	0
Pd ²⁺	-	4.5	0.2
Tl ³⁺	3.4	4.6	0
Au ⁺	4.4	6.5	0.1
Hg ²⁺	4.6	6.8	0
Au ³⁺	-	7.4	2.2

It is interesting to see that the value of α for Au(III) obtained in the present work is higher than those for both Hg(II) and Au(I). It is perhaps somewhat surprising that gold(III) appears to be softer than gold(I); however, Klopman also finds that mercury(II) is softer than gold(I). Edwards⁶⁵ has himself made an estimate of α for Au(III), but his value ($\alpha_{\text{Au(III)}} = 6.5$) is probably less reliable than ours ($\alpha_{\text{Au(III)}} = 7.4$).

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